

Short communication

First record of *Pediobius metallicus* (Hym.: Eulophidae) from Iran

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چکیده

در این بررسی، زنبور *Pediobius metallicus* (Nees) به عنوان پارازیتوئید مگس *Liriomyza* sp. (Dip.: Agromyzidae) از شهرستان زابل (استان سیستان و بلوچستان) جمع‌آوری و شناسایی شد. این زنبور برای فون حشرات ایران رکورد جدیدی محسوب می‌شود.

Eulophidae is one of the largest families in the superfamily Chalcidoidea, including over 4472 species, placed in four subfamilies and 297 genera (Noyes, 2010). Some species are important biological control agent of pests. The first studies on eulophids in Iran were made by Herting (1973) and Davatchi & Shojaei (1989). Ebrahimi *et al.* (2009) and Hesami *et al.* (2010) have also recently collected and identified some eulophid species of Iran.

The genus *Pediobius* Walker is a large genus containing more than 200 species. It is cosmopolitan in distribution, although it is very well represented in the Old World tropics region (Noyes, 2010). This genus has an extremely wide host range. The following eight species of *Pediobius* have already been recorded from Iran: *P. bruchicida* (Rondani) (Askew *et al.*, 2006), *P. illustris* (Waterston) (Boucek & Askew, 1968), *P. cassidae* Erdős, *P. crassicornise* (Thomson), *P. italicus* Boucek, *P. lysis* (Walker), *P. pyrgo* (Walker) and *P. saulius* (Walker) (Yefremova *et al.*, 2007; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2009).

In the current study, a eulophid parasitoid, *Pediobius metallicus* (Nees), belonging to the subfamily Entedoninae, was collected from Zabol, Sistan-Baluchestan province and identified by the last author. This species, which is newly recorded from Iran, is associated with *Liriomyza* sp. (Dip.: Agromyzidae). The specimens were deposited in the collection of the Department of Entomology, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran.

- *Pediobius metallicus* (Nees)

Material examined – Sistan-Baluchestan province, Zabol, 4.iv.2003, 4 ♀♀, 1 ♂, ex: *Liriomyza* sp., leg. E. Rakhshani.

Diagnosis – Female. Body length 1.6-1.7 mm.; vertex and thorax black; compound eyes and ocelli pitchy; antennae 7-segmented, scape and pedicel slender, first funicular segment shorter than pedicel, clava fusiform, pointed; head transverse, short, not impressed; thorax somewhat broad, convex; prothorax transverse, short, visible from above; mesoscutum with well-defined notauli, scutellum hardly longer than broad; gaster short and broad, first segment fairly large and occupying one-third and/or more of the gaster, petiole quadrate to slightly elongate; legs slender, trochanter black, tarsus pitchy; wings brownish, fairly small, submarginal vein strongly tapering at apex, not joining with the parastigma, stigmal vein very short, postmarginal vein shorter than stigmal vein.

Distribution – Europe, Iraq, Pakistan, India and Korea (LaSalle & Parrella, 1991).

This species has been imported into the USA as a biological control agent of Hessian fly, *Mayetiola destructor* (Say) (Dip.: Cecidomyiidae) (Noyes, 2010). This parasitoid is one of the few *Pediobius* species associated with leafminer flies (Dip.: Agromyzidae), as well as other types of hosts, including the families Anthomyiidae, Cecidomyiidae, Chloropidae (Diptera), Elachistidae, Gracillariidae, Nepticulidae and Tortricidae (Lepidoptera) (Noyes, 2010).

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